

NBI 2017 Research Report: Analysis of tunicate fouling on eelgrass habitat at Jackson Point, Nantucket

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Abstract

Eelgrass is a valuable coastal habitat and an ecosystem for a plethora of species that have been in decline due to a number of stressors. Invasive species of tunicates have recently spread to eelgrass in New England, causing additional pressure on an already stressed ecosystem. We wanted to determine if tunicates have spread to eelgrass on Nantucket and therefore surveyed Jackson Point as a representative meadow. The eelgrass meadow at Jackson Point appeared healthy, both in density and canopy height, and not overgrown by epiphytic tunicates. The presence of tunicates, both non-native and native species, on a proximal anthropogenic substrate (town landing dock) confirms that tunicates are in the area. The abundant tunicate (*Botryllus schlosseri*, *Botrylloides violaceus*, *Molgula manhattensis*) coverage on the dock indicated that all available space was occupied during the tunicate reproductive period (summer) and that tunicate propagules had not inhabited the eelgrass. Eelgrass plants immediately adjacent to both sides of the infested dock were not inhabited by tunicates. The site merits on-going monitoring.

Introduction

Tunicates (Ascidiacea) are common marine invertebrate filter feeders that live attached to various natural and anthropogenic substrates in the coastal habitats of New England (van Name 1945; Carman and Roscoe 2003; Pederson 2005; Bullard et al. 2007; Valentine et al. 2007). Up until the 1960's, the Woods Hole, Cape Cod regional tunicate fauna was dominated by native species (Zinn and Abbott 1964) that were minor members of fouling communities, but now the tunicate fauna is dominated by invasive species that are major members of fouling communities (Carman et al. 2007).

It was recently discovered that introduced, non-native tunicates are colonizing eelgrass substrate (Carman and Grunden 2010), leading to numerous detrimental effects on eelgrass community health (Wong and Vercaemer 2012; Colarusso et al. 2016). Eelgrass, *Zostera marina*, is the most common seagrass in New England. Eelgrass meadows are important because they provide numerous geologic and biologic benefits for shorelines, including sediment stabilization, habitat for commercially important species such as fish, crabs, and shellfish (bay scallops), and carbon dioxide absorption (a contributing factor to ocean acidification). Eelgrass is a protected species under the Clean Water Act of the 1970's, and therefore understanding threats to eelgrass is crucial. Eelgrass ecosystems are important and considered a habitat for commercially valuable native species but it can also be habitat for unwanted, non-native species. The number of reports of non-native tunicates in eelgrass beds has recently dramatically increased in the Northeast Pacific (Worcester 1994; Williams 2007; Long and Grosholz 2015) and in the Northwest Atlantic (Carman et al. 2016). Non-native tunicates (Ascidiacea) negatively impact eelgrass substrate by blocking sunlight from reaching blades (Wong and Vercaemer 2014), causing reduced growth rates, taking up space otherwise occupied by epiphytic algae (nutrients for grazers) and juvenile bay scallops, weighing down plant blades (Carman and Grunden 2010), and causing plants to stress and sequester sugars (P. Colarusso, unpublished data). Non-native tunicates also negatively impact shellfish and shellfish aquaculture (Carman et al. 2010; Adams et al. 2011). Further, while the local dispersal of tunicates is attributed to recreational boat

activity and aquaculture transfers (Cohen and Carlton 1998), other vectors may be at play, such as rafting on defoliated eelgrass.

I documented the tunicate population at Nantucket in summer 2016 with NBI support. My work nearby on Martha's Vineyard and Cape Cod documented similar tunicate populations (Carman et al. 2009; Carman et al. 2010; Carman and Grunden 2010; Carman et al. 2016), dominated by non-native species.

For 2017, I proposed to document the biodiversity and density of the tunicate population in eelgrass habitat on Nantucket. The goals and objectives of the NBI study were to: 1) identify the composition and abundance of the tunicate fauna attached to eelgrass, 2) measure the density and canopy height of the eelgrass as a measure of health of the eelgrass, and 3) compare the fauna to other Northwest Atlantic tunicate-eelgrass populations. The goals and objectives of the study were conducted with the assistance of the NBI personnel. Given the proximity of Nantucket to Martha's Vineyard and mainland Massachusetts, I hypothesized that the tunicate fauna on eelgrass at Nantucket will be similar to Martha's Vineyard and Cape Cod, which are dominated by non-native species. The results of the NBI study will be included in a 2017 latitudinal study of tunicates on eelgrass in the Northwest Atlantic, similar to a 2013 latitudinal study (Carman et al. 2016), which documented tunicates in eelgrass from New Jersey to Newfoundland.

While conducting related surveys in eelgrass beds of Martha's Vineyard (Carman et al. 2009; Carman et al. 2010; Carman and Grunden 2010; Carman et al. 2016), I was stung by an apparently new and highly toxic strain of the invasive clinging jellyfish *Gonionemus vertens*. This incident led me to a collaborative effort with Dr. Annette Govindarajan, a cnidarian (jellyfish) expert at WHOI, to document the history and regional distribution of this species (Govindarajan and Carman 2016). Because *Gonionemus* commonly co-occurs where tunicates are in eelgrass meadows, I documented the presence/absence of *G. vertens* during my NBI tunicate surveys. Govindarajan searched eelgrass at Jackson Point for *G. vertens* in summer 2016 and observed tunicates on eelgrass there, but found no *Gonionemus*. Therefore, I planned on formally documenting the Jackson Point occurrence and including it in the 2017 latitudinal study.

Methods and study site

Goal 1: tunicate composition and abundance

We searched for tunicates attached to eelgrass at Nantucket, specifically at Jackson Point, by surveying the eelgrass meadow, with the assistance of NBI personnel and partners. We searched for tunicates by snorkeling and documented their presence/absence and percent coverage. To determine their biodiversity, tunicates were photographed in-situ and identified to the species level. To determine the abundance of tunicates, quadrats (25 cm x 25 cm frames) were placed over eelgrass plants and the content of the quadrats collected. The nearest anthropogenic substrate to the surveyed eelgrass was also surveyed for tunicate diversity and abundance.

Goal 2: eelgrass health measurements

We measured the density and canopy height of the eelgrass within the quadrat samples as standard assessments of eelgrass health. The density of eelgrass is based on the number of eelgrass shoots (plants) per quadrat. The canopy height of eelgrass is based on the length of the

longest leaf per shoot x 80% (after Duarte and Kirkman 2001). The average density and average canopy height per quadrat were then determined and used as standard measurements of the meadow.

Goal 3: comparison to regional eelgrass

I will compare the results of the Nantucket tunicate and eelgrass surveys to other documented reports on tunicates and eelgrass on Martha's Vineyard and Cape Cod and elsewhere in the Northwest Atlantic in the 2013 (Carman et al. 2016) and 2017 latitudinal studies.

Results

Goal 1: tunicate composition and abundance

On July 20, 2017, we conducted a general survey of the eelgrass at Jackson Point, then took 10 random quadrat samples that represented the mid-meadow. The contents of the quadrats were collected in mesh bags and transported to the Brant Point Shellfish Propagation Facility for processing. The nearest artificial substrate to the surveyed eelgrass area was the Jackson Point town landing dock, about 50 m from the meadow. The location of the Jackson Point eelgrass meadow was latitude 41.2757, longitude -70.2016 and the location of the Jackson Point town landing dock was latitude 41.2747, longitude -70.2026.

No tunicates were found on the eelgrass in our general survey and in the quadrat samples. Three species of tunicates were found on the nearest anthropogenic surface at Jackson Point town landing dock, on the sides and bottom of the dock: non-native *Botryllus schlosseri*, non-native *Botrylloides violaceus*, and native *Molgula manhattensis*. Tunicate coverage was 75-100%. All 3 species were documented and vouchered in our 2016 NBI survey of Nantucket and therefore no 2017 voucher specimens were collected.

We did not observe the toxic clinging jellyfish *Gonionemus vertens* at Jackson Point, which is consistent with Govindarajan's findings in 2016.

Goal 2: eelgrass health measurements

The density of the eelgrass ranged from 7-23 shoots/quadrat with an average of 16 shoots \pm 5 S.D. The canopy height of the eelgrass ranged from 16-41 cm/quadrat, with an average of 30 cm \pm 7 S.D. (Table 1).

Goal 3: comparison to regional eelgrass

Jackson Point eelgrass density (average of 16 shoots/quadrat) is similar to eelgrass density on Martha's Vineyard and Cape Cod (averages ranged from 10-49 shoots/quadrat), and elsewhere in the Northwest Atlantic (averages ranged from <1-51 shoots/quadrat). Jackson Point eelgrass canopy height (average of 30 cm) is also consistent with eelgrass canopy height on Martha's Vineyard and Cape Cod (averages ranged from 21-50 cm) and elsewhere in the Northwest Atlantic (averages ranged from 19-80 cm) (Carman et al. 2016).

I will include and compare the results of the 2017 NBI survey at Jackson Point, Nantucket, to other 2017 documented survey reports on tunicate-eelgrass elsewhere in the Northwest Atlantic, collected by my co-investigators on the study (Carman et al., manuscript in prep).

Discussion

The eelgrass at Jackson Point appeared healthy, both in density and canopy height, and not overgrown by epiphytic tunicates. The presence of tunicates, both non-native and native species, on a proximal anthropogenic substrate (town landing dock) confirmed that tunicates were in the area. The near-complete tunicate coverage on the dock indicated that all available space was occupied during the tunicate reproductive period (summer) and that tunicate propagules have not (yet) inhabited the eelgrass. In fact, eelgrass plants immediately adjacent to both sides of the infested dock were not inhabited by tunicates. While we did not find tunicates attached to eelgrass in 2017, they may have been in the past and may be in the future.

The tunicate fauna on the dock (*B. schlosseri*, *B. violaceus*, *M. manhattensis*) also occurred on other artificial substrates on Nantucket in 2016, and elsewhere in New England, including Martha's Vineyard and Cape Cod (Carman et al. 2007; Carman et al. 2009). Interestingly, *B. schlosseri* and *B. violaceus* were the most commonly found tunicates on eelgrass in the 2013 latitudinal study from New Jersey to Newfoundland (Carman et al. 2016). Because of this occurrence, the Jackson Point eelgrass meadow may be vulnerable to tunicate infestation and should be monitored and surveyed for tunicates in the future.

On a separate note, we did not find the epiphytic sponge *Halichondria panacea* on the eelgrass at Jackson Point, which commonly occurs on eelgrass on Martha's Vineyard and elsewhere; only serpulid worm casings were observed on the Jackson Point eelgrass (Figure 1). We observed a great number of large, healthy bay scallops in the eelgrass meadow at Jackson Point, often at 1 ft spacing on the seafloor; this too is different than at Martha's Vineyard and Cape Cod.

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Tables and Figures

Quadrat	# of shoots	longest blade (cm)	canopy height (cm)
1	7	6-34	16
2	15	32-49	34
3	20	22-43	26
4	12	14-43	23
5	19	14-41	24
6	9	15-65	30
7	20	21-63	33
8	22	26-65	34
9	16	21-77	41
10	23	12-51	32

avg 16

avg 30 cm

Table 1. Eelgrass quadrat (25 cm x 25 cm) survey results at Jackson Point, July 20, 2017

Figure 1. Quadrat frame (25 cm x 25 cm) in the eelgrass meadow at Jackson Point, July 2017.
Photo credit: D. Blackwood

Figure 2. Tunicates fouling the bottom of the town landing dock at Jackson Point, July 2017.
Photo credit: D. Blackwood